

A STUDY OF THE PERIODATES OF COPPER.

BY R. K. BAHL AND SURJIT SINGH.

Quaternary cupric paraperiodate was formed by the interaction between disodium paraperiodate ($\text{Na}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$) and copper sulphate, and between paraperiodic acid and copper carbonate. Heptahydrated cupric paraperiodate, was formed by the action of paraperiodic acid on copper acetate. On dehydrating this salt the pentahydrated cupric paraperiodate was formed. The vapour pressures of the hepta- and pentahydrates were found to be 5 mm. and 3 mm. respectively. The trihydrate could not be obtained by further dehydration.

It has been stated (Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", 1922, II, p. 412) that the interaction of copper salts with alkali periodates or paraperiodic acid results in the formation of five periodates of copper. There are, however, many inconsistencies in the results of the previous workers. For example, Rammelsberg (*Ann. Physik*, 1868, **134**, 519) obtained a green powder by treating copper carbonate with paraperiodic acid having the composition 5CuO , I_2O_7 , $5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, cupric paraperiodate pentahydrate $\text{Cu}_5(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, whereas Langlois (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1836, **34**, 257) got a bright green compound, quaternary cupric paraperiodate, Cu_2HIO_6 or $\text{Cu}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}$, H_2O by the same treatment.

The results obtained by us confirm Langlois observations. We have been able to prepare only two salts. The quaternary cupric paraperiodate Cu_2HIO_6 or $\text{Cu}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}$, H_2O and the heptahydrated cupric paraperiodate $\text{Cu}_5(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

A study of the periodates of copper involved:

- (a) The preparation of an alkali periodate and paraperiodic acid, and
- (b) Methods of analysing copper periodates.

(a) Disodium paraperiodate $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$ and paraperiodic acid H_5IO_6 or $\text{HIO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were prepared by Wells' method (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1901, **26**, 278) as modified by Partington and Bahl (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1086). The acid was obtained in the form of transparent, colourless, prismatic crystals, confirming the observations of the latter workers. The melting point of three different specimens prepared at different times was found to be 122° .

(b) Analysis of the periodates of copper :—

(i) The copper was estimated as cupric oxide, by heating a weighed amount of the salt to a constant weight.

(ii) The oxygen in the sample was estimated by the method adopted by Partington and Bahl (*loc. cit.*).

(iii) The iodine was estimated by Kimmis's method as modified by Partington and Bahl (*loc. cit.*). The amount of iodine liberated by the copper present in the salt, was taken into account.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Quaternary Cupric Paraperiodate, Cu₂HIO₆ or Cu₄I₂O₁₁, H₂O.

Preparation.—(A) The fine bluish green suspension of copper carbonate in distilled water was treated with a solution of paraperiodic acid, drop by drop, with continuous stirring. The slow evolution of carbon dioxide at the room temperature became brisk on warming. As the reaction proceeded, the sky-blue precipitate changed first to dark green and finally to yellowish green.

(B) A suspension of disodium paraperiodate Na₂H₃IO₆ (about 3 g. in 20 c.c. of water) was boiled with an excess of copper sulphate solution, that being ensured by the bluish colour of the supernatant liquid, when the precipitate was immediately formed.

The precipitates obtained in the above two methods were filtered, washed and dried at 45° in an electric air oven. The dry salt was a yellowish green powder and was crystalline under the microscope.

The compound was analysed for copper, iodine and oxygen (Table I).

TABLE I.

Sample.	Copper.	Iodine.	Available oxygen.
A) 1	35.80%	37.10%	15.50%
2	35.98	36.20	15.72
3	35.88	36.51	15.70
(B) 1	35.89	37.40	15.25
2	36.10	37.51	15.26
3	35.95	37.08	15.64

The calculated values of copper and iodine are 36.20 and 36.17% respectively. The available oxygen according to the decomposition

is 15.95%.

We were unable to obtain cupric paraperiodate pentahydrate, Cu₂(IO₆)₂ · 5H₂O by the method (A) as claimed by Rammelsberg (*loc. cit.*),

Heptahydrated Cupric Paraperiodate $\text{Cu}_5(\text{IO}_6)_2, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

A dilute solution of paraperiodic acid was added, drop by drop, to a dilute solution of copper acetate. A bright green precipitate thus formed, was filtered, washed and dried at 45° in an electric air oven. The deep green dry salt was analysed.

TABLE II.

Sample.	Copper.	Iodine.	Available oxygen.
1	34.44%	29.10%	12.65%
2	35.43	29.12	12.20
3	34.65	26.5	12.12
4	35.68	29.0	12.62

The calculated values of copper and iodine are 35.83 and 28.54% respectively. The available oxygen according to the decomposition

These results prove definitely that the compound obtained by the above reaction is heptahydrated cupric paraperiodate $\text{Cu}_5(\text{IO}_6)_2, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and not the sky-blue cupric metaperiodate, $\text{Cu}(\text{IO}_4)_2$, as described in the literature (Mellor, *loc. cit.*); the calculated values for the latter being Cu, 14.6% ; I, 54.76% ; O(available), 25.14%.

Effect of Heat on Periodates of Copper.

1. No loss of weight was found by heating quaternary copper paraperiodate, Cu_2HIO_6 or $\text{Cu}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}, \text{H}_2\text{O}$, up to 120° in an electric air oven or upto 110° in vacuum.

2. Heptahydrated copper paraperiodate $\text{Cu}_5(\text{IO}_6)_2, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was taken in an uncovered weighing bottle and heated in an air oven. There was no loss of weight upto 70° . At 74° the dehydration took place yielding pentahydrated copper paraperiodate $\text{Cu}_5(\text{IO}_6)_2, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The dehydration at this temperature was slow and took five hours. There was no further loss upto 120° .

The same salt when heated in a vacuum desiccator dehydrated at a lower temperature 65° , and took 4 hours for completion. There was no further loss upto 100° . The analysis of the pentahydrate is as shown in Table III.

TABLE III.

	1st sample.	2nd sample.	Calculated.
Available oxygen	13.3%	13.13%	13.11%
Copper	37.4	37.32	37.21
Iodine	29.3	29.45	29.75

A study of the vapour pressure of these hydrates confirmed the existence of the pentahydrated copper paraperiodate $\text{Cu}_5(\text{IO}_6)_2, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Vapour pressure of copper salt at 74°.

In these experiments the salt was placed in a small tube, connected with a vacuum pump and a manometer which recorded a high vacuum at the room temperature. The stop-cock connecting the pump was then closed, so that only the tube and the manometer were left connected together. The vapour pressure of the heptahydrate was found to be 5 mm. and that of the pentahydrate to be 3 mm. A mixture of the two hydrates always indicated a vapour pressure of 5 mm. at 74°.

The graph shows the vapour pressures of the two hydrates. The points shown in the graph were obtained by dehydrating the heptahydrate at 74°.